

Nickel(II) Mixed Chelates

R. L. DUTTA and ANJANA BHATTACHARYA

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan 713 101

BESIDES the obvious interest in synthesis, mixed chelate complexes are expected to provide valuable information on magnetic properties, electronic spectra, flexidentate behaviour of polydentate ligands, stereochemical equilibrium etc. In this review the literature on mixed chelates of nickel(II) is surveyed through December 1975. Those chelates which contain at least two different polydentate groups inside the inner sphere are covered. Limited number of nickel(II) complexes containing same two polydentate ligands but with ambidentate coordination, thus making the ligands non-equivalent in respect of attachment, are also reviewed. The complexes are presented in order of decreasing coordination number being sub-classified according to the chromophore system.

A. Coordination Number Six

In an octahedral field the ⁸F Russell Saunders term is split into three components ³A_{2g}, ³T_{2g} and ³T_{1g} in order of increasing energy; ¹D splits into ¹E_g and ¹T_{2g}, ³P changes to ³T_{1g}. Three spin allowed transitions are thus possible: ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g} (ν_1), ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (F) (ν_2), ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (P) (ν_3). These three bands occur in the range 7-13, 11-20, 19-27 kK respectively¹, with molar extinction coefficient 1-10². Two spin forbidden transitions to ¹E_g and ¹T_{2g} are sometimes observed.

Generally octahedral nickel(II) complexes show magnetic moments ranging from 2.9 to 3.4 B.M.². The ³A_{2g} ground term can generate no orbital contribution. However spin orbit coupling mixes the first excited ³T_{2g} (which possesses orbital moment) into the ³A_{2g} term, the mixing-in effect being expressed quantitatively as:

$$\mu = \mu_{s.o.} \left(1 - \frac{4\lambda}{10 Dq} \right)$$

where λ is the spin orbit coupling constant and 10 Dq is the ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g} separation. Since λ is negative for 3d⁸ nickel (II) it follows that moment will be higher the lower the 10 Dq i. e. the weaker the ligand is. Since the 10 Dq value is of the order of 10,000 cm⁻¹, which is very large compared to kT (~210 cm⁻¹ at 25°C), the magnetic moment is not thermally controlled. No low-spin octahedral complex is expected at any crystal field as the ¹E_g excited state runs nearly parallel to the ³A_{2g} ground state.

(i) [NiN₆] chromophore: The compound [Ni(dipy)₂(*o*-phen)]Cl₂⁴ (dipy = α , α' -dipyridyl and *o*-phen = 1,10-phenanthroline) was obtained as pink crystals by the reaction of dichloro (*o*-phen) nickel(II)

with dipy in methanol. A band at ~19.2 kK is likely to be the ν_2 band (Table 1). The compound has been resolved. However the optical isomers racemise rapidly in aqueous solution, which is enhanced by the addition of acid or base. Circular dichroism study of [Ni(*o*-phen)₂(dipy)]²⁺ shows the complex to belong to L configuration⁵. [Ni(*o*-phen)₂(en)]Cl₂⁶ (en = ethylenediamine) was obtained by mixing ice cold ethanolic solution of *o*-phen and [Ni(en)₃]Cl₂. Reaction of [Ni(*o*-phen/dipy)]Cl₂ with stoichiometric amount of en in ice cold solution provides [Ni(en)₂(*o*-phen/dipy)]Cl₂⁵.

[Ni(trien)(en)]X₂^{6,7} (where trien = triethylenetetramine, X = a univalent anion) was prepared (i) by the reaction of [Ni(trien)]X₂ and en in ethanol⁶, or (ii) by mixing equimolecular quantities of the components in ethanol⁷. These are 1:2 electrolytes in methanol. Magnetic moments (3.03 B.M) are in the range of octahedral complexes as also the absorption spectra (bands at 12.0, 19. and 28.8 kK).

Addition of appropriate ligands⁸ in stoichiometric ratio to an aqueous solution of nickel salt, resulted in the isolation of the following complexes [Ni(picmene)-(picam)₂]²⁺, [Ni(picmene)₂(picam)]²⁺, [Ni(picmene)₂(mepic)]²⁺, [Ni(picmene)(picam)(mepic)]²⁺, [Ni(picam)₂(picme)]²⁺ (picmene = 2-methylaminomethylpyridine, picam = 2-aminomethylpyridine, mepic = 2-aminomethyl-6-methylpyridine, picme = 2-(2-aminoethyl pyridine). These compounds behave as 1:2 electrolytes in nitromethane. Low conductance of [Ni(picam)₂(picme)]SO₄.3H₂O in nitromethane and in N,N-dimethylformamide is believed to be due to the sulphate ion being hydrogen bonded in solution. Absorption spectral data (11.10 and 18.25 kK) and magnetic moments (~3.33 B.M) are consistent with octahedral geometry (Table 1).

When a tridentate ligand dpt (1,5,9-triazanonane or dipropylenetriamine) and a bidentate en or pn (propane-1,3-diamine) were added to an aqueous solution of nickel sulphate being followed by the addition of Ba(SCN)₂, a pseudooctahedral [Ni(dpt)(en)(NCS)]⁺ was formed⁹. When Cl, Br, I, ClO₄ etc. were used only five coordinated complexes (with the anions outside the coordination zone) were formed. Three bands (at 10.60, 17.35 and 29.25 kK) with a shoulder at 12.50 kK were recorded for the thiocyanato complex. The magnetic moments were somewhat low (2.8 B.M) (Table 1).

Reaction of en with a solution of [Ni(taz)X₂] (taz = 1,4,8,11-tetraazaundecane (I), X = Cl, ClO₄) in hot

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING [NiN₅] CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK (ϵ_{max})	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Reference
[Ni(dipy) ₂ (<i>o</i> -phen)] ²⁺	Pink	W. 19.23 (14.3)	—	5
[Ni(<i>o</i> -phen) ₂ (dipy)] ²⁺	"	W. 19.23 (14.4)	—	5
[Ni(en) ₂ (dipy)] ²⁺	Purplish red	—	—	5
[Ni(en) ₂ (<i>o</i> -phen)] ²⁺	"	—	—	5
[Ni(<i>o</i> -phen) ₂ (en)] ²⁺	Pink	—	—	5
[Ni(trien)(en)] ²⁺	Pale violet	S. 12.00, 19.00, 28.80 M. 11.00 (10.7), 18.40 (7.9), 28.80 (10.2)	3.03	6
[Ni(picmene)(pic) ₂] ¹⁺	Pink	W. 11.43, 18.45	3.33	8
[Ni(picmene) ₂ (pic)] ²⁺	"	W. 11.11, 18.25	3.12	8
[Ni(picmene) ₂ (mepic)] ²⁺	Buff pink	W. 10.56, 21.55	3.27	8
[Ni(picmene)(pic)(mepic)] ¹⁺	"	W. 10.81, 21.65	3.18	8
[Ni(pic) ₂ (mepic)] ²⁺	Pink	W. 11.10, 18.05	—	8
[Ni(dpt)(en)(NCS)] ⁺	—	S. 10.60, 17.35, 29.25 M. 10.60 (10.4), 12.50 (sh), 17.40 (10.4), 28.20 (8.9) S. 10.90, 18.00, 29.15 M. 10.60 (8.4), 12.3 (sh), 17.50 (8.9) 27.90 (12.7)	2.80	9
[Ni(dpt)(pn)(NCS)] ⁺	—	S. 11.20, 18.50	3.00	9
[Ni(taz)(en)] ²⁺	Mauve	12.50-12.66 (6.8), 19.23 (11.3)	3.16	10
[Ni(pic)(<i>o</i> -phen) ₂] ¹⁺	—	12.50-12.66 (7.0), 19.23-19.42 (11.5)	3.11	11
[Ni(pic)(dipy) ₂] ²⁺	—		2.95	11

W = water, S = solid, M = methanol, pic = picolylamine.

methanol produced the mixed chelate [Ni(taz)(en)]X₂¹⁰.

Mixed chelates of the type [NiLL'₂]Cl₂¹¹ (L = picolylamine, L' = *o*-phen, dipy) were obtained from the interaction of methanol solution of [NiLCl₂]H₂O and L'. Complexes gave expected molar conductance, magnetic moments (~3.0 B.M) and absorption spectra.

Treatment of bis(paludrine) nickel(II) chloride with en is said to yield a mixed chelate [Ni(paldH)₂(en)](OH)₂¹². No magnetic and spectral data are available. This complex is suspected since all attempts in our laboratory to force orange yellow square planar bis(biguanide) nickel(II) to change to an octahedral stereochemistry on the addition of dipy, *o*-phen and en have so far failed.

(ii) [NiN₅O] chromophore: The unusual complex [Ni(*o*-phen)₂(salicylaldiminato)](sal). 3H₂O¹³ (salH = salicylaldehyde) was obtained by mixing bis(salicylal-

diminato) nickel(II) with *o*-phen (1 : 2 ratio) in 98% ethanol. Attempt to prepare mono(*o*-phen) bis(salicylal-diminato) nickel(II) by mixing the components in 1 : 1 ratio in benzene was not successful. The low conductivity value of 18.6 ohms⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹ in nitrobenzene (1 : 1 requires ~25 ohm⁻¹)¹⁴ might be due to some association between anion and cation through hydrogen bonding or due to an equilibrium of the type :

[Ni(*o*-phen)(sal)(salicylaldiminato)] + *o*-phen ...
Magnetic moment of this complex was 3.25 B.M.

Brown crystalline complexes of nickel(II) containing dipy/*o*-phen and pyridine-2, 6-dicarboxylate (dipic), [Ni(*o*-phen/dipy)₂(dipic)]·XH₂O¹⁵, were obtained by reacting [Ni(dipic)(H₂O)₂] with the heterocyclic bases in the ratio 2 : 1. Ir spectra showed the presence of dianionic dipic ligand. ν_1 and ν_2 bands around 9.7 and 18.6 kK and magnetic moment (~3.4 B.M) supported an octahedral geometry (Table 2). Molar conductance of an aqueous solution (60 ohms⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹) indicated incomplete dissociation to [Ni(dipy/*o*-phen)₂(H₂O)₂]²⁺ and dipic²⁻. Since dipy and particularly *o*-phen are quite rigid dipic is likely to be a bidentate ligand. Flexidentate (bidentate) behaviour of dipic has also been observed in the complex [Co(dipic)(BigH)₂]X (BigH = bidentate biguanide)¹⁶.

TABLE 2.—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING $[\text{NiN}_6\text{O}]$ CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK (ϵ_{max})	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Ref.
$[\text{Ni}(\text{salin})(o\text{-phen})]^+$	Orange yellow	—	3.25	13
$[\text{Ni}(o\text{-phen})_2(\text{dipic})]$	Brown	S. 9.70, 18.90	3.41	15
$[\text{Ni}(\text{dipy})_2(\text{dipic})]$	"	S. 9.70, 18.50 W. 9.80 (17.0), 19.10 (7.0)	3.41	15

S = Solid ; W = Water

(iii) $[\text{NiN}_4\text{O}_2]$ chromophore: Blue violet sparingly soluble oxalato-bridged nickel(II) dimers containing diamines, linear tetradentates or macrocyclic ligands (II, III, IV) have been prepared by the action of

(II)

(III)

tet b

(IV)

oxalate (ox) on the respective amine complex of nickel(II)^{17,18}. These possess the formula $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{L})_n(\text{Ox})]\text{X}_2$, (for $\text{L} = \text{en}, \text{pn}$ n is 4 while for (II, III, IV) n is 2). Ir spectra provided the indication of planar symmetrically coordinating oxalate ion. Pseudooctahedral structure was indicated by magnetic moments (2.9 B.M.) and absorption spectra (~ 10 kK, 17 kK and 27 kK) (Table 3). The two oxalato-bridged complexes $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{trien})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ^{17,18}, $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{tet-a})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ¹⁹ (tet-a = V) showed antiferromagnetic coupling in the low temperature magnetic susceptibility curve¹⁹. The oxalate bridge is symmetric in its interaction with the two nickel ions. The unpaired electrons on the two nickel ions are believed to be delocalized into a certain bridge M.O. because of favourable symmetry. This results in an antiferromagnetic interaction which is equivalent to a weak bonding between the two metal ions propagated by the bridging oxalate ligand.

Similar oxalato-bridged complex $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{tat}z)_2(\text{on})]\text{X}_2$ with the ligand $\text{tat}z(\text{VI})$ was prepared by reacting the blue gum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{tat}z)(\text{acac})]\text{ClO}_4$ with oxalic acid²⁰.

tet a

(V)

tat z

(VI)

Complexes containing bidentate nitrate or acetate group with en or taz are known to have octahedral structure from their magnetic moments and electronic spectral data¹⁰ (Table 3).

Mixed chelates²¹ with ligands en, pn or tet-b along with a bidentate nitrate group were obtained by reacting nickel nitrate hexahydrate with the amine in hot methanol. Infrared spectra were indicative of bidentate coordination of one nitrate (bands at 806, 1280, 1490, 695 and 745 cm^{-1}) in all the complexes, while the second nitrate was ionic (bands at 1375, 825, 704 cm^{-1}). From a comparison of their reflectance spectra (Table 3) with that of $[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_2(\text{OH})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ coordinated bidentate nitrate was believed to be higher than water in the spectrochemical series. However it is disturbing to note that $[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_2(\text{NO}_3)]\text{ClO}_4$ with bidentate nitrate, as well, absorbs at about the same energy (10.6 kK) as $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{en})_4\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}_2$ (10.2 kK) with bridging chloride ion.

In the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{N-N-SMe})_2\text{NO}_3]\text{NO}_3$ ²², both the nitrate group and the ligand (VII) behaved as bidentate donors, the latter as (N-N). The presence of bands at 1480, 1340, 1275 cm^{-1} in ir spectra indicated ionic and coordinated nitrate.

N-N-SMe

(VII)

From absorption spectra, magnetic moment and ir spectra the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{mepic})_2(\text{NO}_3)]\text{ClO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (mepic = 2-aminomethyl-6-methyl pyridine) was considered octahedral with a bidentate nitrate group. The complex containing bidentate NO_2 group was also found to be octahedral. These complexes did not obey the spectrochemical series. Since two mepic molecules could not produce a planar ligand field²⁴ the 1:2 mepic mixed chelates with octahedral environment must have the cis configuration. Absorption spectra in aqueous solution (Table 3) indicated the presence of $[\text{Ni}(\text{mepic})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2]^{2+}$ species. Dq values of these complexes were smaller than those of the corresponding en, picH (picolinic acid) and dipy complexes²⁵.

(iv) $[\text{NiN}_3\text{O}_3]$ chromophore: $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{dien})_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{Ox})]\text{X}_2 \cdot 17\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (X = NO_3 , ClO_4) complexes have a bidentate bridging oxalate. The complexes attained a pseudooctahedral structure by incorporating a water molecule in each coordination sphere (Table 4).

$[\text{Ni}(\text{EDDA})]$ reacts with amino acids (AAH) e.g. glycine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid, α , β -diaminopropionic acid to form $[\text{Ni}(\text{EDDA})(\text{AA})]^{3+}$.

Spectral data and magnetic moments (3.1 BM) of $[\text{Ni}(\text{dipy}/o\text{-phen})(\text{dipic})\text{X}]\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were in conformity with the formulation $[\text{Ni}(\text{dipy}/o\text{-phen})(\text{dipic})(\text{OH}_2)]$

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING $[\text{NiN}_3\text{O}_3]$ CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK (ϵ_{max})	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Ref.
$[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_2]\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Blue violet	S. 10.80, 17.60, 27.20	3.00	17
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tet}-b)]_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$	"	S. 10.10, 17.20, 27.20	2.95	17,18
$[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_2(\text{NO}_3)]^+$	Lilac blue	10.60, 17.50, 27.30	3.10	21
$[\text{Ni}(\text{tet}-b)(\text{NO}_3)]^+$	"	10.70, 17.50, 27.30	3.09	21
$[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_2(\text{OAC})]^+$	"	10.60, 17.60	3.12	10
$[\text{Ni}(\text{taz})(\text{OAC})]^+$	"	11.00, 18.50	3.12	10
$[\text{Ni}(\text{N}-\text{N}-\text{SMe})_2(\text{NO}_3)]^+$	Yellow	11.20, 17.80, 23.00 (sh)	3.10	22
$[\text{Ni}(\text{mepic})_2(\text{NO}_3)]^+$	—	S. 10.40, 17.10, 27.50 W. 10.10 (11.0), 13.30 (sh), 16.70 (sh), 27.50 (11.0)	3.14	23
$[\text{Ni}(\text{gly})_2(\text{en})]$	—	S. 10.50, 13.00, 17.30, 28.10	—	29

S = Solid ; W = Water

Diaquo bis (salicylaldehydato) nickel(II) (1 mol) reacted with *o*-phen (2 mols) to form a complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal})(o\text{-phen})_2]^+ \text{sal}^- \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ which had molar conductance value 19.0 ohm^{-1} in nitrobenzene. This also suggested the existence of an equilibrium similar to equation (1). When the above reaction is carried out in 1:1 molar ratio mixed chelates of the type $[\text{Ni}(o\text{-phen})(\text{sal})_2]$ are obtained (A-V).

Nickel(II) glycinate reacted with acetone and 2-aminoethanol to give $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_2\text{C}:\text{NCH}_2\text{CO}_2)(\text{NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CO}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{N.C}_2\text{H}_4\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$. 2-aminoethanol was coordinated through nitrogen alone and it offered steric hindrance for condensation of the second Me_2CO molecule.

The complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_2\text{-NH.COO})_2(\text{en})]^{2+}$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{DA})(\text{en})]^{2+}$ ($\text{DAH}_2 = \text{diacetylhydrazine}$) and $[\text{Ni}(\text{gly})_2(\text{en})]^{2+}$ ($\text{glyH} = \text{glycine}$) are believed to have octahedral structure from absorption spectra. For example $[\text{Ni}(\text{gly})_2(\text{en})]$ showed bands at 10.5 (13.0), 17.3 and 28.1 kK (Table 3).

Extensive n.m.r. study has been done on $[\text{Ni}(\text{EDDA})(\text{en})]^{2+}$, where EDDA ($\text{EDDAH}_2 = \text{ethylenediamine diacetic acid}$) behaved as quadridentate ligand. Magnetic and electronic spectral data are not available.

Molar conductivity in aqueous solution indicated some dissociation :

$[\text{NiL}(\text{NO}_3)_2]^{2+}$ (L is diethylenetriamine (dien) or pip (VIII)) serve as examples of monodentate and bidentate coordination of nitrate groups (bands at 1455 , 1298 cm^{-1} (monodentate NO_3) and at 1502 , 1272 cm^{-1} (bidentate NO_3)). Electronic spectra and magnetic moment support octahedral geometry (Table 4).

(VIII)

Six coordination in $[\text{Ni}(\text{pip})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ is attained by a monodentate (Ni-O, $2.027 \text{ \AA}$) and a nearly symmetrical bidentate (Ni-O, 2.138 ; Ni-O, $2.070 \text{ \AA}$) nitrate group.

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING $[\text{NiN}_2\text{O}_4]$ CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK (ϵ_{max})	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Ref.
$[\text{Ni}(\text{dien})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	Turquoise blue	S. 10.40, 16.60, 26.70	3.17	21
$[\text{Ni}(\text{dien})(\text{OH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{C}_2\text{O}_4]^{2+}$	—	—	2.94	17
$[\text{Ni}(\text{dipy})(\text{dipic})(\text{OH}_2)_2]$	Blue	S. 9.30, 17.50, 28.20 (sh)	3.10	19
$[\text{Ni}(o\text{-phen})(\text{dipic})(\text{OH}_2)_2]$	Blue	S. 9.70, 16.90 25.00 (sh)	3.08	19
$[\text{Ni}(\text{pip})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	Red brown	S. 11.50, 12.70 (sh), 20.00	3.17	31
$[\text{Ni}(\text{salgly})(\text{dipy})(\text{OH}_2)_2]$	Light green	S. 11.10, 17.10		
		M. 11.24 (20.1), 17.39 (15.8)	3.14	32
$[\text{Ni}(\text{sal-alan})(o\text{-phen})(\text{OH}_2)_2]$	"	S. 11.10, 17.10		
		M. 11.30 (14.5), 17.35 (9.3)	3.14	32
$[\text{Ni}(5,6\text{-benzosalgly})(\text{dipy})(\text{OH}_2)_2]$	Brownish green	M. 11.49 (22.0), 18.18 (15.8)	3.18	32

S = Solid ; W = Water

Preparation of mixed chelates $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{dipy}/o\text{-phen})(\text{OH}_2)_2]\text{XH}_2\text{O}^{33}$, where LH_2 is a tridentate dibasic Schiff base derived from salH or 5,6-benzosalicylaldehyde (5,6-benzosalH) with glycine, dl- α -alanine (α -alanH), β -alanine (β -alanH), l-leucine (leuH) and dl-valine (valH), was effected by four routes: (i) interaction of $\text{dipy}/o\text{-phen}$ with NiL_2 , (ii) from a mixture of all components in ethanol in presence of sodium acetate, (iii) by the reaction of $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal})_2(\text{dipy}/o\text{-phen})]$ with amino acid, (iv) reaction between $[\text{Ni}(\text{gly})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2]$, $\text{dipy}/o\text{-phen}$ and hydroxyaldehyde. All complexes showed pseudooctahedral structure on the basis of their electronic spectra and magnetic moment (Table 4). Almost all complexes exhibit two slightly overlapping pyrolysis bands due to loss of lattice water and coordinated water, which is followed by a major decomposition profile giving NiO . The ir spectra were consistent with the presence of coordinated $\text{C}=\text{N}$, COO^- , H_2O and the heterocyclic bases.

v) $[\text{NiN}_2\text{O}_4]$ chromophore: The 1:1:1 complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{tmen})(\text{acac}/\text{bzac})(\text{OH}_2)_2]\text{ClO}_4^{33}$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{tmen})(\text{acac}/\text{bzac})(\text{NO}_3)_2]^{33}$ (tmen = N,N,N',N'-tetramethylethylenediamine, acacH = acetylacetone, bzacH = benzoylacetone) were obtained by mixing appropriate nickel(II) salt in ethanol with a solution of the hetero ligands in chloroform followed by the addition of sodium carbonate. The $[\text{Ni}(\text{tmen})(\beta\text{-diketonato})_2]^{33,34}$ complexes were prepared by shaking with sodium carbonate a mixture of nickel sulphate hexahydrate in water and the heteroligands in chloroform. For nitrate chelates ir spectra gave indication of bidentate coordination of nitrate ion. Solid state spectra showed (Table 5) octahedral coordination of ligands in all the above mentioned complexes. The blue diaquo perchlorate formed a red solution in an inert solvent and the spectrum was similar to that of the anhydrous red perchlorate in the same solvent. This indicated that the two water molecules were loosely bound to the nickel atom. In coordinating solvents the coordinated nitrate of $[\text{Ni}(\text{tmen})(\beta\text{-dik})(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ is substituted by solvent molecules. The perchlorate or tetraphenyl borate salts provide blue colour at lower temperature in coordinating solvents while at higher temperature a red colour appears.

An interesting class of mixed chelates containing Schiff base (IX) derived from the condensation of aldehydes (or ketones) with NN dialkylethylenediamine and the corresponding aldehydes (or ketones) as participating ligands have been reported^{35,36}. $[\text{Ni}(\text{salNR}_2)(\text{sal})]^{35}$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{hacNR}_2)(\text{hac})]$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{hprNR}_2)(\text{hpr})]$ ($\text{salNR}_2\text{H}=\text{salicylidene N}$, Nalkylethylenediamine, $\text{hacNR}_2\text{H}=\text{Schiff base of 2-hydroxyacetophenone}$ and NN-alkylethylenediamine, $\text{hacH}=\text{2-hydroxyacetophenone}$, $\text{hprNR}_2=\text{Schiff base of 2-hydroxypropionophenone}$ and NN-alkylethylenediamine, $\text{hprH}=\text{2-hydroxypropionophenone}$) were obtained by two routes³⁵. a) A solution of the Schiff base in dry tetrahydrofuran was treated with potassium-t-butoxide and $(\text{Et}_4\text{N})_2\text{NiBr}_4$. b) The second route involved the reaction of diaquo bis(salicylaldehydato/ketonato) nickel(II) with NN-dialkylethylenediamine in toluene. The complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{salMe}_2)(\text{sal})_2]$ could be obtained from (c) $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{salNMe}_2)_2]$ or (d) $[\text{Ni}(\text{salNMe}_2)_2]$ and salH in toluene. Method (b) and (c) were used to prepare complex $[\text{Ni}(5,6\text{-benzosalNR}_2)(5,6\text{-benzosal})]^{35}$. Molecular weight measurements in bromoform showed

When $\text{R}' = \text{H}, \text{SalNR}_2$
 $\text{R}' = \text{CH}_3, \text{hacNR}_2$
 $\text{R}' = \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, \text{hprNR}_2$

(IX)

that all the complexes were dimeric (X) except $[\text{Ni}(5,6\text{-benzosalNR}_2)(5,6\text{-benzosal})]$ which was a monomer. In ir spectra $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ were identified at $1590\text{-}1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1617\text{-}1648\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Only for $[\text{Ni}(5,6\text{-benzosalNR}_2)(5,6\text{-benzosal})]\text{XH}_2\text{O}$ a band in the region $3450\text{-}3510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was obtained which was indicative of the presence of coordinated water. In solid state dimer complexes showed three bands which were assigned as ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}$ (F) $\sim 10.7\text{ kK}$, ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{E}$ (D) $\sim 13.3\text{ kK}$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ (F) $\sim 16.4\text{ kK}$ (Table 5) in

pseudooctahedral stereochemistry. A fourth band at ~7.5 kK characteristic of five coordinate nickel(II) was

(X)

found in CHCl₃ solution even at -14°C. Reversible spectral changes suggested that in CHCl₃ solution the following equilibrium exists :

The electronic spectra and magnetic moment (~3.1 B M) supported the six-coordinated structure of [Ni(5,6-benzosalNR₂)₂(5,6-benzosal)(OH₂)]. These mono-aquo complexes lost the coordinated water molecule on heating in vacuum to form five coordinated amorphous brown products. This type of dehydration was also possible for compounds [Ni(acac)(5,6-benzosalNR₂)(OH₂)]³⁶, [Ni(bzac)(5,6-benzosalNR₂)(OH₂)]³⁶, [Ni(acac)(salNR₂)(OH₂)]³⁷, [Ni(acac)(hacNR₂)(OH₂)]³⁷. All of these complexes were prepared by

following the three general procedures given for [Ni(acac)(salNR₂)(OH₂)]³⁷. Molecular weight, IR spectra, electronic absorption spectra and magnetic moments justified the pseudooctahedral geometry of the aquo complexes. The thermodynamics of the equilibrium

(A=bidentate ligand, B=tridentate ligand) was studied at various temperatures using spectral data^{36,37}. The enthalpy and entropy parameters ΔH° and ΔS° have values close to -13 KCal mole⁻¹ and -35 eu respectively. Increase of concentration of water in the solvent and decrease of temperature resulted in an increase in the concentration of the five coordinated species. The behaviour of these complexes was in contrast to that of [Ni(salNR₂)(sal)]₂ and the difference could be explained if it were assumed that the phenolic oxygen of the salicylaldehyde was a better bridging atom than the acac oxygen.

Mixed chelates [NiA₂E]³⁸ were prepared from [Ni(acac)₂]₃ and substituted en in 1 : 3 ratio in boiling toluene. Complexes were characterised as octahedral monomers by molecular weight, absorption spectra (three bands) and magnetic moment measurements. It is interesting to note that during synthesis the ligands do not react to form Schiff bases, as was evident from the persistence of the ν_{N-H} (3150-3400 cm⁻¹) and ν_{C=O} (1520 cm⁻¹) bands.

TABLE 5—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING [NiN₂O₄] CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK (ε _m α _m)	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Ref.
[Ni(tmen)(acac)(OH ₂) ₂] [†]	Blue	Ac. 9.51 (8.0), 16.26 (7.4), 20.49 (14.1)	3.28	33
[Ni(tmen)(bzac)(OH ₂) ₂] [†]	Bluish green	Ac. 9.43(8.9), 16.00 (8.7), 20.33 (16.4)	3.14	33
[Ni(tmen)(bzac)(NO ₂) ₂]	"	Ac. 9.52 (10.4), 16.21 (19.6)	3.19	33
[Ni(tmen)(bzac) ₂]	"	Ac. 9.55 (10.9), 16.34 (10.6)	3.27	33
[Ni(tmen)(acac) ₂]	Blue	D. 9.41 (10.4), 16.05 (8.5)	3.27	33
[Ni(tmen)(dpm) ₂]	"	DCE. 9.67 (1.4), 16.45 (9.7)	3.09	34
[Ni(tmen)(dbm)(OH ₂) ₂]	Green	Ac. 9.51 (9.6), 16.50 (10.1), 19.60 (sh)	3.12	34
[Ni(tmen)(dbm)(NO ₂) ₂]	"	Ac. 9.61 (12.4), 16.29 (26.04)	3.07	34
[Ni(tmen)(dbm) ₂]	"	Ac. 9.67, 16.50	3.03	34
[Ni(tmen)(tfa)(NO ₂) ₂]	Blue	Ac. 9.73 (15.2), 16.18 (30.1)	3.12	34
[Ni(tmen)(tfa) ₂]	"	D. 9.75 (9.8), 16.29 (9.4)	3.10	34
[Ni(tmen)(hfa) ₂]	Green	D. 10.12 (9.0), 16.31 (13.5)	3.13	34
[Ni(5,6-benzosal)(5,6-benzosal NMe ₂)(OH ₂) ₂]	Brownish green	S. 11.00, 13.16, 17.25	3.16	36
[Ni(acac)(salNMe ₂)(OH ₂) ₂]	"	S. 11.10, 13.00, 16.95	3.26	37
[Ni(acac)(hacNMe ₂)(OH ₂) ₂]	"	S. 11.10, 13.00, 16.55	3.29	37
[Ni(acac) ₂ (een)]	—	9.80 (16.0), 13.00 (4.0), 16.80 (11.0)	3.17	38
[Ni(acac) ₂ (deen)]	—	9.50 (15.0), 13.00 (3.0), 16.40 (10.0)	3.35	38
[Ni(acac) ₂ (dben)]	—	9.50 (15.0), 13.00 (3.0), 16.40 (11.0)	3.22	38
[Ni(bzacac) ₂ (o-phen)]	Yellow green	S. 9.64, 16.81	—	40
[Ni(w-nac) ₂ (dipy)]	Light green	DCM. 10.00 (11.9), 10.00 (7.7) (sh), 17.5 (20.6), 21.1 (8.0)	—	41
[Ni(en)(dhnap)(OH ₂) ₂]	Blue	S. 19.60, 24.40	2.81	42
[Ni(dipy)(cat)(OH ₂) ₂]	—	14.92, 17.85 (59.0)	2.91	43
[Ni ₂ (dppn)(SO ₄) ₂]	Green	S. 10.20, 16.75	2.87	45
[Ni ₂ (Me ₆ dppn)(NO ₃) ₂]	"	S. 10.00, 16.40	2.80	45
[Ni(mpfc)(mpicH)(EtOH)(Br)]	"	S. 7.69, 14.39	3.12	49
[Ni(dipy)(sal) ₂]	"	S. 10.20, 16.70	3.19	50
[Ni(dipy)(5,6-benzosal) ₂]	Light green	S. 10.60, 17.20	3.17	50
[Ni(o-phen)(5-Cl-sal) ₂]	Yellowish green	C. 10.60 (12.2), 17.24 (23.0) C. 10.21 (11.1), 16.66 (20.8)	3.24	50

Ac = acetone, D = dimethylformamide, DCE = dichloroethane, DCM = dichloromethane, C = chloroform.

Mixed complexes containing β -diketones (e.g. acacH, bzacacH (3-benzylacetylacetone), ω -nacH (ω -nitroacetophenone) and dipy or *o*-phen, was synthesised via reaction of bis(β diketonato) nickel(II) and the heterocyclic bases³⁹⁻⁴¹. X-ray³⁹, TGA³⁹, nmr³⁹ and absorption spectra⁴⁰ were carried out and octahedral geometry was established (Table 5).

Blue coloured mixed complexes of the type [Ni(A)(B)(OH₂)₂]^{42,43} (A=en, propylenediamine (pen), dipy and BH₂=catechol (catH₂), pyrogallol, 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene (dhnaph₂) were prepared from the components in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio. Pseudooctahedral geometry was suggested from absorption spectra and magnetic moment. Their stability constants⁴² were evaluated by pH metric titration.

(Aci-nitromethyl) benzenato ion (XI), nickel(II) nitrate and tmen in 50% ethanol water gave green crystals of bis[(aci-nitromethyl) benzenato] (tmen) nickel(II)⁴⁴. Single crystal X-ray study⁴⁴ showed the nickel atom was in an environment of six coordination

Acini nitro methylbenzenato ion

(XI)

through two nitrogens of tmen and four oxygen of two (aci-nitromethyl) benzenato ions.

Mixed chelates, [Ni₂(dppn)(SO₄)₂], [Ni₂(Me₂dppn)(NO₃)₄] (XII) (dppn = 3, 6-di(pyrid-2-yl)(pyridazine) were prepared from NiSO₄.6H₂O or Ni(NO₃)₂.6H₂O and the appropriate ligand⁴⁵. The electronic spectra registered two bands at 10.2 kK (³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}) and 16.5 kK (³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}) (Table 5). For nitrate complexes, presence of strong bands at 1300 and 1450 cm⁻¹ and two bands around 825 cm⁻¹ indicated both uni- and bidentate nitrate groups. For sulphato complexes, bidentate coordination of sulphate was indicated (bands at 480, 960 and 1100 cm⁻¹). Magnetic susceptibility studies between 80-300° K showed antiferromagnetic exchange in the binuclear complexes (XII). The super exchange mechanism involves excitation of an electron from the t_{2g} into the e_g orbitals of Ni²⁺, the unpaired spins in t_{2g} orbitals coupling by overlapping with π -molecular orbitals of the bridging ligand.

The complex Ni(phen-O)₂(NO₃)₂⁴⁶ serves as an example of bidentate coordination of nitrate.

R = H, dppn,
A = CH₃, Me₂dppn,
O = nitrate oxygen

(XII)

phen - O
(XIII)

The octahedral complexes [NiT₂(dipy/*o*-phen)]⁴⁷ (T = tropolonate anion) and [Ni(en)(5,6-benzosalicyl)₂]⁴⁸ (5,6-benzosalicyl)H = 5,6-benzosalicylic acid) were prepared and their properties studied. ν_{Ni-O} and ν_{Ni-N} were detected in the tropolonate mixed complexes⁴⁷.

tropolone

(XIV)

Complexes of 6-methylpyridine-2-carboxylic acid (mpicH) were isolated from alcoholic solution containing mpicH and nickel(II) halide⁴⁹. One ligand behaves as a neutral donor and the other is coordinated as anion of the acid. Reflectance spectra and magnetic moment were explained in terms of octahedral geometry. Thermogravimetric analysis showed first the loss of alcohol followed by loss of CO₂ finally changing to NiO.

Complexes of formula [Ni(A)₂B]⁵⁰ (where A = anion of hydroxyaldehyde or hydroxyketone. e.g. salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde (5-ClSalH), 5, 6-benzosalicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hacH), B = dipy or *o*-phen) were prepared by the interaction of [Ni(A)₂(OH₂)₂] and B in 1 : 1 ratio. These complexes are also pseudooctahedral as evident from their electronic spectra and magnetic moments (~3.2 B.M). Ir spectra were consistent with the presence of the heterocyclic donor and C=O group. It is hoped that these complexes will serve as precursors in template reactions with chosen amines and amino acids.

vi) [NiN₂S₂] chromophore: Some analytically useful complexes of nickel(II) with dithizone (dzH) and heterocyclic nitrogen bases e.g. *o*-phen, dipy were prepared by the reaction of *o*-phen/dipy with nickel dithizonate in CHCl₃⁵¹. Equilibrium constants of the adduct formation were determined in CHCl₃ solution by spectrophotometric method (log K, 4.63, 5.96)⁵¹. For [Ni(dz)₂(dipy)], ΔS° and ΔH° are -2.1 and -6.4 respectively. Magnetic moment (~2.8 B.M) and spectra indicated octahedral structure. The crystal structure determination⁵² of the dipy adduct showed an octahedral environment with two sulphur atoms in cis position.

vii) [NiN₂S₂O₂] chromophore: A number of pseudooctahedral adducts were prepared from Ni(L)₂ and B, (L=monothio β -diketonate ion⁵³, fluorinated monothio- β -diketonate ion⁵⁴, thiomaltolate⁵⁵ ion and B = dipy, *o*-phen, mephen (2-methyl-1, 10-phenanthroline) terpy terpyridine. The ir spectra of [NiL₂(terpy)]

indicates the presence of both coordinated and uncoordinated carbonyl groups. One of the L groups thus functions as a monodentate sulphur donor. When both the alkyl groups were methyl no extra band appeared in ir spectra for $\nu_{C=O}$ and no splitting occurred in C-S bond, so that there were two possibilities: (i) a seven coordinated structure with tridentate terpyridyl or (ii) an almost regular octahedral structure with a bidentate terpyridyl. Solution absorption spectra showed two bands (ν_1, ν_2).

B. Coordination Number Five

A trigonal bipyramidal (D_{3h}) and a square pyramidal (C_{4v}) geometry are possible for five coordination. Complexes may be high spin or low spin. High spin complexes generally exhibit magnetic moment from 3.0 to 3.45 B.M.⁵⁰ while low spin complexes are diamagnetic. High spin complexes with D_{3h} symmetry exhibit seven bands between 7.0 kK to 26 kK due to spin allowed transitions from ${}^3E'$ to ${}^3E''$ (F), ${}^3A_1''$ (F),

TABLE 6—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING $[NiN_2S_2O]$ CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK (ϵ_{max})	Magnetic moments in B. M.	Ref.
$[Ni(RC(S)=CHCOR)_2(dipy)]$ R=Me R'=OMe	Buff	S. 10.50, 16.70	3.16	53
$[Ni(RC(S)=CHCOR)_2(o\text{-phen})]$ R=Me R'=Me	Reddish brown	S. 10.90, 18.70	3.23	53
$[Ni(RC(S)=CHCOR)_2(terpy)]$ R=Me R'=Me	Brown	S. 10.60, 17.70	3.20	53
$[Ni(RC(S)=CHCOR)_2(mephen)]$ R=Me R'=OMe	Buff	S. 10.20, 14.50	3.12	53
$[Ni(RC(S)=CHCOR)_2(o\text{-phen})]$ R=CMe ₂ R'=CMe ₃	Light brown	S. 10.50, 16.70	3.20	53
$[Ni(MeC(S)=CHCOCF_3)_2(dipy)]$	Green	—	3.15	54
$[Ni(MeC(S)=CHCOCF_3)_2(o\text{-phen})]$	—	—	3.34	54
$[Ni(MeC(S)=CHCOCF_3)_2(terpy)]$	Light brown	—	3.15	54
$[Ni(thiomalto)_2(dipy)]$	Brown	—	3.10	55
$[Ni(thiomalto)_2(o\text{-phen})]$	Medium brown	—	2.91	55

S = Solid

viii) $[NiN_2S_4]$ chromophore: Bis(diaryldithiophosphinato) nickel(II) reacts with dipy⁵⁶, o-phen⁵⁶, en⁵⁷ and DMGH⁵⁸ (dimethylglyoxime) (B) in 1:1 ratio to provide green adducts of the type $[Ni(R_2PS_2)_2(B)]$. Spectra of these compounds exhibited two broad bands around 9.0 kK and 14.5 kK (Table 7), which were assigned as ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ in octahedral field. Magnetic moment (3.0 B.M) was also consistent.

${}^3A_{2g}'(F)$, ${}^3E''(P)$, ${}^3A_{2g}'(P)$ and spin forbidden transitions to ${}^1E''(D)$ and ${}^1E''(D)^{61}$. Two principal absorption bands (~17.0 kK and 26.0 kK) have been found in low spin complexes with D_{3h} symmetry. These are assigned as ${}^1A_1' \rightarrow {}^1E'$ and ${}^1A_1' \rightarrow {}^1E''$. High spin complexes of C_{4v} symmetry also exhibit bands in the same region due to spin allowed transitions from ${}^3B_1(F)$ to ${}^3E(F)$, ${}^3A_2(F)$, ${}^3B_2(F)$, ${}^3E_2(F)$, ${}^3A_3(P)$, ${}^3E(P)^{61}$. The reported electronic spectra of low spin

TABLE 7—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING $[NiN_2S_4]$ CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK (ϵ_{max})	Magnetic moments in B. M.	Ref.
$[Ni(Medtpi)_2(o\text{-phen})]$	Greenish yellow	S. 9.00, 14.40, 21.70 (sh) C. 9.00 (20.0), 14.30 (40.0)	3.06	56
$[Ni(dtpi)_2(dipy)]$	Pale green	S. 9.80, 14.60, 18.5 (sh)	2.58	56
$[Ni(dtpi)_2(DMGH)]$	"	S. 9.70, 15.00	3.07	58

S = Solid; C = Chloroform

Structure determination of 1,10-phenanthroline bis (0,0'-dimethyldithiophosphato) nickel(II)⁵⁹ showed that the o-phen molecule occupied cis position about nickel(II). The four Ni-S distances of the two somewhat constrained four membered rings were approximately equal (2.49 Å).

The synthesis of the complex was achieved via reaction of the planar bis (chelate) compound with the heterocyclic nitrogen base.

distorted square pyramidal nickel(II) complexes generally show one ligand field band in the range 18.0 kK - 20.0 kK with a number of more or less evident shoulders on the low energy side⁶². In some cases, however, a nearly symmetrical band is found, which is similar in shape and frequency to that assigned to the $b_2 \rightarrow b_1$ transition in square planar nickel(II) complexes. Electronic spectra often fail to distinguish unambiguously between a square planar geometry and a low spin square pyramidal geometry⁶².

(i) $[NiN_3]$ chromophore: Only one series of complexes is known having formula $[Ni(dpt)(L)]X_2^9$ (dpt = dipropylentriamine; L = en or pn, X = Cl, Br, I, ClO_4 , BPh_4). These complexes are high spin, pale violet and soluble in methanol. From ir, uv, visible spectra, conductivity and magnetic susceptibility data they were supposed to have square pyramidal geometry in the solid state. Only one compound $[Ni(dpt)(pn)]I_2$ showed an intermediate^{6,8} configuration between trigonal bi-pyramidal and square pyramidal geometry. In all the cases μ_{eff} values were lower (~ 2.9 B.M.) (Table 8) than that (0.3-4.5 B.M.)¹⁰ for high spin 5-coordinated nickel(II) complexes. Since these values were found to be constant over the temperature range -160° to $+80^\circ C$ with a zero Weiss constant the possibility of spin state equilibrium was excluded. The low value was assumed to originate from small orbital contribution.

of the 5-Cl derivative showed one Schiff base ligand to be tridentate and the other as bidentate with the $-N(C_2H_5)_2$ group free. The geometry of the compound was a distorted square pyramid (XV) in which the nickel(II) lay a little above the basal plane. These compounds were the first examples of high spin five

(XV)

TABLE 8—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING $[NiN_3]$ CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral band in kK (ϵ_{max})	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Structure proposed	Ref.
$[Ni(dpt)(en)]$	Pale violet	S. 7.1, 8.3, 11.2, 18.5, 29.4 M. 11.3 (6.9), 12.7 (sh), 18.5 (5.7), 29.0(6.0)	2.80	Square-pyramidal	9
$[Ni(dpt)(pn)]$	"	S. 7.1, 8.3, 10.0, 17.5, 28.6 M. 9.7 (4.3), 17.6 (10.0), 27.6 (15.8)	2.91	"	9

S = Solid; M = Methanol

(ii) $[NiN_3O_2]$ chromophore: Some bis (Schiff base) nickel(II) complexes behaved as five-coordinated species although the Schiff bases were potentially tridentate^{5,4,6,6}. These were prepared by the reaction of substituted diaquo bis (salicylaldehydato) nickel(II) with appropriate N, N-substituted ethylenediamine, and have the general formula $[Ni(X-salNR_2)_2]^{6,4}$. When R is C_2H_5 these compounds were found to possess three types of configuration in the solid state dependent on the substituent X. When X is 3-Cl, 5-Cl or 3,4 benzo the reflectance spectra of the compounds having μ_{eff} 3.24-3.30 B. M., showed four bands around 7.7, 10.0, 12.8, 16.2 kK (Table 9). X-ray structural analysis^{6,8}

coordinated nickel(II). When the five coordinate complex $[Ni(5-Cl-sal-NEt_2)_2]$ was treated with bis (N-isopropyl-3-chlorosalicylaldiminato) nickel (II)^{6,6} ($[Ni(3Cl-salNPr^i)_2]_2$) a mixed chelate $[Ni(5-Cl-salNEt_2)(3-Cl-salNPr^i)]^{6,7}$ was isolated, which gave a magnetic moment 3.20 B. M and absorption bands at 7.6 kK ($\epsilon = 35.5$); 10.0 kK ($\epsilon = 23.5$); 12.8 kK ($\epsilon = 16.0$); 16.12 kK ($\epsilon = 49.5$).

(iii) $[NiN_3O_2]$ chromophore: On dehydrating $[Ni(\beta-dik)(5,6-benzosalNR_2)(OH_2)]^{6,6}$, $[Ni(\beta-dik)(salNR_2)(OH_2)]^{3,7}$, $[Ni(5,6-benzosal)(5,6-benzosalNR_2)]$

Table 9—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL (II) CONTAINING $[NiN_3O_2]$ CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral band in kK (ϵ_{max})	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Structure proposed	Ref.
$[Ni(3-Cl-salNEt_2)_2]$	—	C. 7.69 (16.7), 10.0 (11.5), 12.74 (7.3), 16.13 (59.8)	3.30	Square-pyramidal	64,65
$[Ni(5-Cl-salNEt_2)_2]$	—	C. 7.69 (46.4), 10.0 (38.5), 12.74 (17.5), 16.13 (44.4)	3.30	"	64,65
$[Ni(3,4-benz-salNEt_2)_2]$	—	C. 7.69 (56.4), 10.0 (31.8), 12.74 (20.8), 16.18 (49.7)	3.24	"	64,65

C = Chloroform

(OH₂)]³⁶ (section A v) glassy brown materials with pentacoordinated square pyramidal structure were obtained. These have a distinguishing band at ~7.3 kK in the solid state spectra which was assigned as ³B₁→³E, other bands being due to transitions ³B₁→³A₂, ³B₂ and ⁴E (10.4, 11.4, 13.0, 16.5 kK) (Table 10). The solution spectra showed increasing concentration of octahedral species with increasing concentration of water and decreasing temperature.

dithiophosphate ligands and through two nitrogen atoms of *o*-phen. The two Ni-N distances were identical and a bit shorter than the Ni-N distance of six coordinated adduct, α, α' dipyriddy bis(0,0'-dimethyldithiophosphato) nickel(II)⁶⁹. The three Ni-S distances were, however, unequal. The structure was best viewed as an intermediate between trigonal bipyramid and square pyramid. Evidently one dithiophosphate ligand was monodentate sulphur donor.

TABLE 10—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND GEOMETRY OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL (II) CONTAINING [NiN₂O₃] CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral band in kK (ε _{max})	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Structure proposed	Ref.
[Ni(acac)(5,6-benzoalNET ₂)]	Brown	S. 7.20, 10.40, 11.40, 13.05, 16.55	—	Square pyramidal	36
[Ni(bzac)(5,6-benzoalNET ₂)]	„	S. 7.30, 10.40, 11.50, 13.10, 16.55	—	„	36
[Ni(acac)(salNMe ₂)]	„	S. 7.35, 10.60, 11.50, 13.00, 16.50	—	„	37
[Ni(acac)(5-Cl-salNET ₂)]	„	S. 7.30, 10.50, 11.60, 13.00, 16.80	—	„	37

S = Solid

(iv) [NiNO₃] chromophore: The complex Ni(hac)(hacNET₂)⁸⁵ was a dimer and was believed to be different from its analogs (section A-v). The bands at 7.4, 11.0, 12.9 and 16.6 kK are assigned as ³B₁→³E, ³A₂, ³B₂ and ³E respectively. Five coordination could be satisfied by either of the following two structures (XVI), (XVII):

(XVI)

(XVII)

(vi) [NiAs₂] chromophore: In 1950 Nyholm⁶⁹ reported a diamagnetic compound of formula [Ni(diars)₃]ClO₄ (diars=*o*-phenylene bis(dimethylarsine)) having a tris (bidentate) octahedral structure. X-ray studies⁷⁰ have subsequently shown that the compound was in reality *o*-phenylene bis (dimethylarsine) [bis (*o*-dimethylarsinophenyl) methylarsine] nickel(II) where the nickel atom was placed in a regular tetragonal pyramidal environment of five arsenic atoms. This compound was afterwards prepared directly⁷⁰ from diars, triars (bis(*o*-dimethylarsinophenyl) methylarsine) and nickel perchlorate hexahydrate in ethanol-ether medium. The compound was diamagnetic and the spectrum was very similar to that of the Nyholm compound. Thus the reported claim of Nyholm to have prepared the first octahedral nickel(II) complex with S=0 proved untrue. In fact Tanabe-Sugano diagram

TABLE 11—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND GEOMETRY OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL (II) CONTAINING [NiNO₃] CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral band in kK (ε _{max})	Magnetic moment in B. M.	Structure proposed	Ref.
[Ni(acac)(hacNMe ₂)]	Brown	S. 7.1, 10.6, 11.6, 13.0, 16.7	—	Square-pyramidal	37
[Ni(hac)(hacNET ₂)]	Green	S. 7.4, 11.0, 12.9, 16.0	3.26	„	35

S = Solid

(v) [NiN₂S₃] chromophore: The addition of 2,9-dimethyl-1, 10-phenanthroline to bis (0,0'-dimethyldithiophosphato) nickel(II)⁸⁹ resulted in a high spin (3.03 B.M) five coordinate mixed chelate. The crystal and molecular structure⁸⁸ showed nickel(II) was coordinated through three sulphur atoms of the two

of d⁸ ion shows that at no crystal field strength can we have S=0 as the ground state. The diamagnetism of the complex is in conformity with the Sacconi rule that a low spin five coordinate complex will result when the sum of the Allred-Rochow electronegativities of the donor atoms lies below 13.⁷¹

C. Coordination Number Four

Most of the four coordinated nickel(II) mixed complexes are square planar and diamagnetic. They exhibit a strong absorption band in the region 15 to 25 kK with ϵ value ~ 60 . A second band is found at 23-30 kK.⁷² These two bands are assigned as ν_2 and ν_3 respectively. ν_1 is found only for a few complex. ν_2 and ν_3 are generally assigned as ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions. In tetrahedral nickel complexes one multiple band ~ 15 kK and another band ~ 7 kK are found due to transitions ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ (ν_3) and ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_2(F)$ (ν_2) respectively. Lifting of degeneracy of $T_1(P)$ due to spin orbit coupling gives multiplicity to the ν_3 band. In certain circumstances the ν_1 band can be observed around 4-5 kK.⁷³ The molar extinction coefficients of tetrahedral complexes are ~ 200 . Very few mixed chelates or tetrahedral geometry are so far known only in solution. Magnetic moment for tetrahedral nickel(II) are around 4.0 B.M.⁷⁴ Since the ground state is a 3T_1 term which carries orbital contribution the moment values are significantly above the spin-only value of 2.83 B.M.

(i) $[NiN_4]$ chromophore: Paramagnetic complexes $NiLL'$ (XVIII)^{75,76} where L and L' are different aminotroponimine ligands, are formed in solution by mixing a bis (aminotroponiminato) nickel(II), (which is in equilibrium of square planar and tetrahedral geometry) and a different aminotroponimine ligand. The equilibria

are attained very rapidly in non-polar solvents at room temperature. Analysis of the pmr spectra of the solution showed delocalization of spin density from metal to the ligand by $d\pi - \pi$ bonding. One ligand gained in spin density at the expense of the other ligand. This was affected by the electron-withdrawing or electron-donating substituents. Geometry of the complexes is believed to be tetrahedral. Delocalisation of spin density is believed to be due to effective overlap of $d\pi$ orbitals of nickel(II)

with π orbitals of the aminotroponimine. It has been suggested that the ground state is 3E (configuration $e^3b_2^1$) rather than 3A_2 ($b_2^2e^2$) in the homochelate while in the mixed complex it is 3B_1 ($b_2^2b_1^1a_1^1$). The a_1 ($d_{x^2-y^2}$) orbital is σ -bonding only while the b_1 (d_{xz}) orbital can participate in π -bonding with one chelate ring only.

(ii) $[NiN_3O]$ chromophore: Nyholm et al^{77,78} prepared a compound bis (4-iminopentane-2, 3-dione-

3-oximato) nickel(II) by the reaction of bis (pentane-2, 4-dionato) nickel(II) with KNO_2 and ammonium acetate in water or aqueous alcohol or by the reaction of nickel acetate, pentane-2,4-dione with an excess of KNO_2 and ammonium acetate. Taylor and Ewbank⁷⁹ prepared the same compound by the reaction of 3-hydroxy-iminopentane-2,4-dione with aqueous ammoniacal solution of nickel acetate at room temperature. 4-imino-2, 3-pentanedione 3-oxime has four donor atoms (2N, 2O) of which only two can coordinate to a single metal ion, so that ambidentate behaviour was expected from this ligand. The structure was investigated by pmr, ir and mass spectrometry⁸⁰.

Five different structures proposed by earlier workers were rejected on the basis of pmr evidence. pmr spectra showed four distinct methyl resonances in equal ratio, which is satisfied by structure (XIX) alone. The complex has thus an unsymmetrical structure (XIX) in which one ligand (IAI) is coordinated through two nitrogen atoms while the other (IAI') through one nitrogen and one oxygen atom.

(XIX)

A similar chelation was also supported in bis(1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-iminopropane-1-one oximato) nickel(II) $[Ni(IEI)(IEI')]^{80}$

Ambidentate coordination was also shown by the nickel(II) chelate containing 4-methyliminopentane 2,3-dione-3-oxime (MeIAIH) and one iminopentane 2,3-dione-3-oxime (IAIH)⁸¹

Diamagnetic, nonelectrolyte and monomeric compounds $[Ni(RIAI)(IAI')]^{82}$ (where R=benzyl (Bz), isopropyl (iPr)) were prepared by refluxing a suspension of $[Ni(IAI)(IAI')]$ with alkylamine in alcohol-chloroform mixture. Electronic spectra in chloroform were very similar to that of $[Ni(IAI)(IAI')]$ (Table 12). Failure to prepare $[Ni(RIAI)_2]$ by direct reaction from its components suggests enough steric hindrance provided by the two R groups.

The nonelectrolyte mixed complexes $[Ni(RIEI)(IEI)]^{83}$ (R=H, CH_3 , C_2H_5 , C_3H_7 , C_4H_9 , C_2H_4OH) were obtained from nickel acetate, required amine RNH_2 , NH_4OH , isonitrosoethylacetoacetate in 50% aqueous alcohol. The complexes are diamagnetic and monomers. Their absorption spectra supported square planar geometry. Ir spectra indicated that the carbonyl group was non-coordinated and one of the N-H hydro-

TABLE 12—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND GEOMETRY OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING [NiN₂O] CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK (ε _{max})	Magnetic moments in B. M.	Structure proposed	Ref.
[Ni(IAI)(IAI')]	Red	22.20 (sh), 28.60, 33.90 (sh), 36.00	dia	Square-planar	82
[Ni(MeIAI)(IAI')]	Yellowish brown	22.70, 28.60, 33.30 (sh), 35.60	dia	"	82
[Ni(BzIAI)(IAI')]	"	27.3 (sh), 28.40, 33.30 (sh), 35.70	dia	"	82
[Ni(iPr-IAI)(IAI')]	Yellow	22.7 (sh), 28.60, 33.60 (sh), 36.00	dia	"	82
[Ni(IEI)(IEI')]	"	26.0 (sh), 29.90, 33.10, 39.7	dia	"	83
[Ni(MeIEI)(IEI')]	Orange		dia	"	83
[Ni(C ₂ H ₄ OHIEI)(IEI')]	Yellow orange		dia	"	83

dia=diamagnetic.

gens of [Ni(IEI)(IEI')] was replaced by alkyl group. This fact was further supported by pmr spectra since only one N-H proton signal was obtained.

[Ni(IMI)(IMI')]⁸⁴ (IMI=isonitrosomethylacetoacetateimine), [Ni(IBI)(IBI')]⁸⁴ (IBI=isonitrosobenzoylacetoneimine), [Ni(IANI)(IANI')]⁸⁴ (IANI=isonitrosoacetanilideimine) were prepared by methods described by Nyholm^{77,78} and Ewbank⁷⁹. The complexes were monomeric, nonelectrolyte and diamagnetic. Infrared, pmr and visible spectra have been made use of in elucidating the structures of these complexes. In all the above formulations the primed ligands are coordinated through one nitrogen and one oxygen while the non-primed ones are linked to nickel(II) through two nitrogens.

(iii) [NiN₂O₂] chromophore : A series of mixed chelates, [Ni(tmen)(β-dik)]X^{3,34} (β-dikH=β-diketone, X=ClO₄, B(Ph)₄) were prepared by drying [Ni(tmen)(β-dik)(OH₂)₂]ClO₄ (section A-(v) over P₂O₅ under reduced pressure, colour changing from blue to red. The tetraphenyl borate salts were obtained by treating [Ni(tmen)(β-dik)(NO₃)] in 1, 2-dichloroethane with sodiumtetraphenylborate. The electronic spectra of the red perchlorate and tetraphenyl borates in an inert solvent are diagnostic of square planar geometry. In coordinating solvents the colour was green or blue due to the equilibrium :

The amount of red species increased in the order methanol << ethanol < n-propanol < acetone << CHCl₃ or C₂H₄Cl₂⁸⁵. The equilibrium was shifted to the left hand side with increasing temperature.

Mixed chelates of nickel(II) containing one thiopicolinamide and one β-diketone⁸⁶ were obtained by a) the reaction of bis(2,4-pentanedionato) nickel(II) with bis(N-alkyl-thiopicolinamidato) nickel(II) in 1 : 1 molar ratio in benzene, or b) the reaction of N-alkylthiopicolinamide (XX) and bis(2,4-pentanedionato) nickel(II) in

(XX)

chloroform. These are nonelectrolytes and have magnetic moments in solution ranging from 0 to 0.62 B.M. When the alkyl group in thiopicolinamide ligand was of relatively small size, the ligand was able to coordinate only through nitrogens, giving [NiN₂O₂] chromophore.

TABLE 13—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND GEOMETRY OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING [NiN₂O₂] CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK (ε _{max})	Magnetic moments in B. M.	Structure proposed	Ref.
[Ni(tmen)(acac)] ⁺	Red	Ac. 9.51 (7.9), 16.26 (7.4), 20.53 (21.8)	0.57	Square-planar	33
[Ni(tmen)(bzac)] ⁺	"	Ac. 9.43 (9.2), 16.18 (9.0), 20.49 (17.4)	0.23	"	33
[Ni(tmen)(dpm)] ⁺	"	Ac. 9.45 (4.6), 15.90 (sh), 20.37 (56.5)	dia	"	34
[Ni(tmen)(dbm)]	"	Ac. 9.49 (9.3), 16.03 (9.7), 20.00 (sh)	dia	"	34
[Ni(tmen)(tfa)] ⁺	"	Ac. 9.57 (7.8), 15.87 (7.6)	dia	"	34

Ac = Acetone

Equilibration of two differently substituted bis(salicylaldiminato) nickel(II) in deuteriochloroform results in rapid ligand exchange giving paramagnetic, tetrahedral mixed chelates (XXI)⁷. The mixed chelates have been unambiguously identified by their pmr spectra, with characteristic isotropic proton hyperfine contact interactions. Calculation of spin densities in the two chelate rings shows that an asymmetric redistribution of spin has occurred. The authors believe that the primary path of exchange involves a direct bimolecular collision of two paramagnetic, tetrahedral homo-chelates, which is then followed by the rupture of two Ni-N or

(XXI)

two Ni-O bonds resulting in the formation of the mixed chelate. It is interesting to note that such paramagnetic mixed chelates were formed only in those cases where the individual chelates showed square planar $\rightleftharpoons$ tetrahedral equilibrium in solution.

(iv) [$NiNO_3S$] chromophore: With a bulky substituent in the thiopicolinamide group (XX) as in (N-sec/terbutylthiopicolinamidato) (2,4-pentanedionato) nickel(II)⁸, the thiopicolinamide ligand behaved as an SN donor, the spectra being different from those of the complexes with small alkyl groups as substituents.

(v) [NiN_2S_2] chromophore: A series of orange coloured neutral square planar nickel(II) complexes containing dithiolene and α -diimine ligand have been reported^{9,10}. The dithiolenes used in this study were (S-S, R where R = CN, CF₃, Ph and α -di-imine ligands used were (N N, R₂, R₃), *o*-phenylenediamine, biacetyl-bisanil, 1,10-phenanthroline, 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline

etc. The mixed chelates were prepared by three general reactions. (a) Substitution of one dithiolene ligand of a bis(dithiolene) complex by a diimine ligand. (b) Substitution of one diimine ligand of bis(diimine) nickel(II) complex by a dithiolene ligand. (c) Interaction of bis(diimine) nickel(II) and bis(dithiolene) nickel(II). All complexes showed some low energy high intensity transitions in the region 12-20kK and some high intensity absorption bands in the region 28-45 (Table 14)kK. From solvatochromism studies it was concluded that the ground state of the mixed chelates were dipolar. A decrease in the frequency of the low frequency intense transition was brought about by electron-withdrawing substituents on the diimine ligand and an increase was forced by electron-withdrawing substituents on the dithiolene ligand. This fact indicated that the dithiolene character in the populated low energy excited state was less than the dithiolene character of the depopulated ground state orbital, whereas the diimine character was greater in the excited state orbital than in the ground state orbital⁹. The spectral fact supported the asymmetric valence electron distribution through the metal atom. The mixed chelates undergo two one-electron reductions and one-electron oxidation. Thus a four membered electron transfer series with overall charge Z = +1, 0, -1 and -2 exists.

(vi) [NiS_4] chromophore: Mixed dithio-perthio-carboxylato nickel(II) complexes¹¹ (RCS₂) (RCS₃)Ni were obtained by three methods; (a) by oxidation of dithiocarboxylates with sulphur, e.g. Ni(dtbc)(dtbs)^{12,13}, (b) by partial desulphuration of bis perthiocarboxylato complexes, e.g. Ni(dtt)(dtts)¹⁴, (c) from equimolar mixture of bis thio and bis perthio-carboxylates of nickel(II) in inert solvents. These mixed compounds were more stable with aromatic substituents. They are monomeric. Structure determination¹⁵ of the complex (R=4-propylphenyl) confirmed the square planar geometry. The absorption spectra in solid state and in solution showed a considerable shift in the band $\sim$ 13 kK (Table 15). Apart from this band a high intensity band $\sim$ 19 kK and a shoulder $\sim$ 23 kK were present. For aliphatic compounds the whole spectrum shifted by $\sim$ 2 kK to higher energy.

TABLE 14 - ELECTRONIC SPECTRA, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND GEOMETRY OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING [NiN_2S_2] CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK	Magnetic moments in B. M.	Structure proposed	Ref.
[Ni(S-S, ph)(<i>o</i> -phen)]	Blue black	S. 18.70, 20.00, 23.00, 26.20, 29.60 DCM. 19.35, 20.50, 23.50, 29.60 (sh), 37.90, 44.90	—	Square planar	90
[Ni(S-S, CN)(N-N, CH ₃ , ph)]	Violet black	S. 15.40, 17.10, 18.50, 24.00, 28.40 DCM. 15.60, 16.50 (sh), 24.00 (sh), 27.00 (sh), 36.00	—	"	90
[Ni(S-S, CN)(N-N, CH ₃ , <i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄)]	Red black	S. 16.2 (sh), 17.55, 27.5	—	"	90

S = Solid; DCM = dichloromethane

TABLE 15—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND GEOMETRY OF THE MIXED CHELATES OF NICKEL(II) CONTAINING $[\text{NiS}_4]$ CHROMOPHORE.

Compound	Colour in solid state	Absorption spectral bands in kK	Magnetic moments in B. M.	Structure proposed	Ref.
$[\text{Ni}(\text{dtb})(\text{dtbs})]$	—	S. 12.6 (sh), 17.9 (sh), 18.2, 21.3, 29.8, 33.9	dia	Square planar	93
$[\text{Ni}(\text{dtt})(\text{dttts})]$	—	S. 12.6 (sh), 18.2 (sh), 18.9, 21.7	dia	"	93

S = Solid

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